

Haplotype-Resolved Chromosome-scale Assembly of the Bighead Catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) Genome

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ABSTRACT

We sequenced the complete genome of the Thai bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*), a species native to Thailand and Vietnam, used in aquaculture and of significant ecological importance. A haplotype-resolved diploid representations of a third-generation sequencing-based genome assembly was constructed from PacBio HiFi, Oxford Nanopore, Hi-C, and Illumina paired-end sequencing technologies for Bighead catfish. The diploid assembly was rigorously validated, manually curated, and scaffolded using Hi-C long-range interactions. It achieved a haploid genome size of 880 Mb distributed across 27 pseudo-chromosomes, exhibiting high continuity (N50 = 35.4 Mb), completeness (BUSCO = 95.5%), and accuracy (QV50, corresponding to 99.999% correctness). This first chromosome-scale genome sequence for *C. macrocephalus* addresses a critical gap in genomic resources for the *Clarias* genus. It will provide valuable insights into the genetic basis of aquaculture traits, support conservation efforts for wild populations in the Mekong River, and enable advances in selective breeding studies. Additionally, the genome will aid in constructing a *C. macrocephalus* pan-genome graph and serve as an anchoring reference for future genomic research leveraging next-generation sequencing for aquaculture. The haplotype-resolved assembly offers unique insights into potential genomic rearrangements arising from decades of selective breeding with other species, such as the North African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*). It also facilitates the study of structural variations and genetic introgression, contributing to population-level assessments of genetic diversity and aquaculture improvement. This genomic resource aligns with the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) 2 (Zero Hunger). All assembly data are publicly available under Zenodo archive number DOI [10.5281/zenodo.14826876](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14826876) and under NCBI BioProject number [PRJNA1121957](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/PRJNA1121957).

Background & Summary

The Thai bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) is a freshwater catfish species native to Southeast Asia, primarily inhabiting the Mekong River basin across Cambodia, Thailand, and Vietnam, with introduced populations in China, Guam, Malaysia, and the Philippines¹⁻³. As a member of the family Clariidae within the order Siluriformes (regrouping all 3000 other extent catfish species), *C. macrocephalus* shares a close evolutionary relationship with the white-spotted catfish (*Clarias fuscus*, both having diverged approximately from each other at around 25 million years ago)⁴, also related, though more distantly, to the North African catfish (*Clarias gariepinus*) and the eel catfish (*Channallabes apus*)⁵⁻⁷. The species was first described by Günther in 1864, *C. macrocephalus* has historically been misidentified as the walking catfish (*C. batrachus*) which is another species of catfish with near-identical morphological and phenotypical features, however subsequent studies have successfully clarified the distinct taxonomy and ecological traits of both species⁸. The species is a benthopelagic, facultative air-breather, allowing it to survive in low-oxygen environments and even move across land. Its ability to bury in mud during dry seasons and migrate between water bodies is supported by specific anatomical and behavioral adaptations. Further information about bighead catfish is available on the FishBase website (<https://www.fishbase.se/summary/clarias-macrocephalus.html>).

Although aquaculture practices and ecological research-based public-knowledge advances exist, there is a gap in genetic resources for the species and genomic data remain unperfect⁹, and out-of-date¹⁰, thereby constraining potential efforts for biodiversity conservation, selective breeding, and overall sustainable aquaculture development. Therefore, here, we try to address a long-standing lack of genomic resources for *C. macrocephalus* by presenting the first high-quality, chromosome-scale, haplotype-resolved genome assembly for the bighead catfish.

Methods

Bighead Catfish, DNA Sequencing

The bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*) was raised in the experimental aquaculture ponds of the Faculty of Fisheries at Kasetsart University in Bangkok, Thailand. The specimen was a one-year-old adult (developmental stage), male (sex), and sexually mature (reproductive status) and healthy (disease state). The subject was terminated, and its sex was determined based on external gonad morphology and histology observations, following established protocols^{11,12} (data not shown). The genomic DNA was extracted from liver tissue (DNA source) by salting-out DNA (treatment)¹³ and the bighead catfish genome was sequenced using a combination of 3-rd generation sequencing to an initial coverage of approximately 10-fold using Pacific Biosciences (PacBio) High-Fidelity (HiFi) Circular Consensus (CSS) data¹⁴, about 30-fold using Oxford Nanopore Technology (ONT) long-read data¹⁵, and 2-nd generation short-read sequencing to an initial coverage of around 36-fold using paired-end (PE), 151 base-pair Short-Reads (SR). The short-read data included proximity-ligation (Hi-C Illumina) reads used in Hi-C scaffolding^{16,17} and standard Illumina reads¹⁸.

Read Survey and Genome Survey

We calculated sequencing depth (i.e., the genome coverage in term of mapped sequenced DNA reads) based on genome size estimates from the genome survey, results are shown in **(Figure 1A)**. The genome survey was conducted with GenomeScope2.0¹⁹ and KAT (K-mer Analysis Toolkit)²⁰, results were an estimated genome coverage below 13X for HiFi long-read data, and a genome coverage below 40X, for standard Illumina and Hi-C Illumina short-read data, we also estimated between-haplotype nucleotide heterozygosity at around 0.521% and duplication levels at 1.77%, with repetitive elements comprising over 35% of the genome, and finally the haploid genome size was predicted to be around 890 Mb **(Figure 1B)**. **Figure 1C** and **Figure 1D** illustrate the quality assessment of raw long-read sequencing data, where the x-axis represents read length (in base pairs) and the y-axis represents median individual read quality. The PacBio HiFi sequencing data resulted in a mapped genome depth (post-assembly) of less than 10× but was of high quality **(Figure 1C)**. In contrast, the ONT sequencing data showed a mapped genome depth of less than 4×, with a median read N50 of 13 kb and a longest read of 137 kb **(Figure 1D)**. Further details are provided in the Supplementary Methods sections.

Genome Assembly Strategy Overview

The genome of *Clarias macrocephalus* was assembled using a hybrid strategy integrating PacBio HiFi (accurate long reads), Oxford Nanopore (long reads), Illumina paired-end (short reads), and Hi-C proximity ligation data **(Figure 1)**. These complementary data types facilitated haplotype resolution and scaffold anchoring and allow to generate dual assemblies from a single diploid tissue. Dual assemblies are representations of a diploid genome characterized by two sets of homologous contigs with each set representing one complete haploid genome and each loci more or less heterozygous. Similar to contigs in a primary assembly, contigs in a dual assembly may have occasional switches between parental haplotypes (<https://lh3.github.io/2021/10/10/introducing-dual-assembly>). Dual assemblies can sometimes infer parental haplotype attribution (e.g., in F1 hybrids where one of two parental species is distinct from the other). More recently, base-methylation data (information stored in raw HiFi CSS reads) was used to separate maternal and paternal haplotigs²¹. Finally dual assemblies can decrease sequencing costs, and are advantageous relative to trio assemblies, when we cannot obtain enough DNA or don't have access to parental samples. The need of more data is particularly problematic for clinical samples, and for wild or farmed bighead catfishes sampled in the rivers ponds²². Therefore "Dual" is the type of assembly performed in this paper.

Among the tested assemblers (Hifiasm, Flye, wtdbg2), we selected Hifiasm for the haplotype-resolved assembly because of its ability to separate parental haplotypes (phasing) on low genome coverage (< 13X) HiFi data. In contrast, Flye and wtdbg2 produced collapsed consensus assemblies. Below, we outline the main steps for the final approach in assembling bighead catfish haplotype 1 and haplotype 2:

- 1. Initial Assembly Generation (Contigging and Phasing):** Contigging is the process of assembling overlapping DNA reads into continuous sequences without gaps (i.e., contigs). These contigs are then separated and assigned to a phase group using proximity-ligation data (Hi-C) based on their parental origin and spacial physical distance in the cell nucleus. Therefore a contig that comes from an haplotype is referred as an haplotig and in a diploid phased assembly there are two groups of homologous haplotigs (i.e., unitigs, one per haploid "homotype" haplotype). In an unphased assembly, a contig may join alleles from different parental haplotypes in a diploid or polyploid genome; see²³ and <https://lh3.github.io/2021/04/17/concepts-in-phased-assemblies> while the process of separating sequences based on their parental haplotypes in diploid genomes is referred to as "haplotype phasing". Here, Hifiasm was used in "Hi-C UL" mode²² to generate a haplotype-resolved assembly using Hi-C + ONT + HiFi reads **(Figure 2D, left)**, followed by GreenHill²⁴ using all data types: Hi-C + Illumina + ONT + HiFi reads for further

scaffolding and phasing of the haplotigs (**Figure 2E**), and finally NextPolish²⁵ was employed with HiFi and Illumina short reads correcting small errors at the nucleotide level (i.e., SNPs) while preventing allele switching between homologous haplotypes (switch errors). This produced two phased contig sets representing homologous haplotypes (**Supplementary Figure 1**).

- 2. Hi-C Scaffolding and Their Validation:** Scaffolds are computationally ordered and oriented arrays of contigs that have sequence gaps along their length. The process of scaffolding of contigs is about arranging and orienting contigs into larger structures, sometimes with gaps, using additional data like proximity ligation (Hi-C) or optical maps in order to reconstruct an in-silico equivalent to the Karyotype (referred to as Scaffotype) which consists of Hi-C scaffolds of "pseudo-chromosomes" (i.e., chromosome pseudomolecules), visualized as Hi-C maps. Prior to Hi-C scaffolding misassembly corrections are done using CRAQ²⁶, then Hi-C scaffolds (contigs and scaffolds) are flipped, reoriented, and refined to improve structural accuracy, this is the "manual review" step, performed using JBAT (JuiceBox Assembly Tools)¹⁶, this is followed by a "post-review" step which seals contigs (i.e., by creating gaps between new adjacent contigs) to form Hi-C scaffolds to ultimately reconstruct pseudo-chromosomes followed by 3D-DNA "post-review" validation¹⁶ (**Figure 2F**). Finally more gaps were closed with TGS-GapCloser²⁷ (**Figure 2G**). This step (**Figure 2F**) can be repeated if necessary after polishing of contigs (**Figure 2H**) and usually results in well-defined Hi-C scaffold pseudo-chromosomes (**Figure 2C**).
- 3. Assembly Polishing of Contigs and Benchmarking:** Polishing a genome assembly consist in correcting sequencing errors using additional data (meryl k-mer databases, long-reads and short-reads). To further improve assembly accuracy, reads were aligned to the polished assembly, the three primary long-read mappers employed were Winnowmap²⁸, Minimap²⁹, and VerityMap³⁰ (previously known as TandemTools) was used for was used for assembly validation only. Mapping quality was ensured by removing secondary alignments, low-quality regions (MAPQ0), and hard-clipped reads. This step was crucial for validating assembly completeness and reducing errors. Non-haplotype-aware tools (e.g., Racon, Clair3) were applied cautiously to minimize errors from parental haplotype switches, while Merfin³¹ filtered edits for polishing and BCFtools consensus produced the final polished sequence. For large variants and closing gaps using read alignments we used Sniffles2³² for large structural variant (SV) calling, specifically for insertions (INS) and deletions (DEL). We evaluate genome quality in term of errors found in the assembly that are not found in raw reads, for that we calculate the Quality Value of a genome assembly where QV refers to the Phred quality score (or quality (Q) score), an integer representing the estimated probability of an error (i.e., that a base is incorrect). If P is the error probability, then it follows the equation $P = 10^{-Q/10}$, where $Q = -10\log_{10}(P)$. The polishing workflow implemented here for correcting bighead catfish ensured high nucleotide accuracy Quality Values (from initial QV33 to around QV > 46) after Benchmarking against recommended assembly metrics, from the VGP paper⁷.

Additional assemblies produced are described in the Supplementary Methods. Methodological details are presented in the following sections and in **Figure 2**.

[Main assembly] De Novo Haplotype-Resolved Assembly, Hi-C Scaffolding and Haplotype Phasing

The haplotype-resolved diploid assembly of bighead catfish combined HiFi, ONT, and Hi-C data using Hifiasm ('-hic -hifi -ul -primary')³³ v0.19.8-r603, resulting in two Hi-C-phased contig sets (.hic.hap1 and .hic.hap2), representing two separate and complete haploid homologous haplotypes²². To scaffold haplotype 1 and haplotype 2 with long reads (HiFi and ONT), proximity-ligation (Hi-C), and Illumina paired-end short reads, we used GreenHill ('-cph \$hap1 \$hap2 -p \$combined_ont_hifi -IP1 -IP2 -HIC')²⁴ v1.0.0.

[Main assembly] Hi-C Maps, Manual Review, and Post-Review for Obtaining Chromosome-Scale Scaffolds

To build heatmaps of Hi-C contacts between pair of loci and obtain Hi-C scaffolds (post haplotype resolved assembly), we used the Juicer pipeline ('-assembly -S early')³⁴ v2.17.00 and Hi-CCUPS CPU ('-ignore-sparse -cpu') v2.17.00, which aligned Hi-C reads the sequence data to GreenHill scaffolds and assign a mapping quality score using BWA-MEM³⁵ v0.7.17_r1188. PCR duplicates and near duplicate mapped reads were removed using Samtools³⁶ v1.18. Hi-C contacts were generated at various resolutions (2.5 Mb to 5 kb). Visualization of Hi-C maps was performed using the script run-assembly-visualizer.sh from the 3D-DNA pipeline¹⁶ v02/12/2018. To manually review Hi-C scaffolds for misjoins or errors, Juicebox Assembly Tools (JBAT)³⁴ v2.16.00 was used, and regions with misjoins or under-collapsed heterozygosity were edited based on off-diagonal signals in the Hi-C read density heatmap, indicating contig/scaffolding errors. Post-review validation of Hi-C scaffolds was performed using the 3D-DNA-post-review.sh v180114 ('-sort-output -c 27'), a module of the 3D-DNA pipeline¹⁶. Unplaced scaffolds were filtered using SeqKit ('-by-length -reverse -m 2,500,000')³⁷ v2.7.0, resulting in 27 chromosome-length scaffolds per haplotype.

[Main assembly] Haplotype-Aware Genome Polishing with NextPolish2

With the goal of increasing assembly quality QV values and correcting small SV errors (SNV/indels), we generated a HiFi mapping file after counting repetitive k-mers in reads with Meryl (k=15) for Winnowmap, a version of Minimap2 optimized for read alignment in repetitive regions which leverages a bloom filter to filter alignments based on k-mer multiplicity^{28,38}. Next we generated two k-mer databases (21-mer and 31-mer files) from trimmed short-reads using the Yak k-mer analyzer (<https://github.com/lh3/yak>). The Winnowmap mapping file in BAM format, the target assembly in FASTA format, and the two yak databases in yak format were used as input for genome polishing with NextPolish2²⁵ v0.2.0.

[Main assembly] Align-Genus and Read-Homology-Based Methods for Gap-Filling and Joining of Contigs

To resolve assembly gaps (i.e., gaps between contigs in pseudo-chromosomes/scaffolds), homology-based approaches were used³⁹. For this purpose, additional scaffold sets were generated using Hifiasm ('-primary') as contigger, by varying the type of read data input (HiFi, ONT, Hi-C) and the haplotype purging options ('-l0'). Additionally, orthologous sequences were retrieved from NCBI Datasets for closely related species in the family Clariidae (Taxonomy ID: 13012, n = 3 reference sequences): *C. fuscus* (GCA_030347435.1), *C. gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2), and *Channallabes apus* (GCA_030522415.1), last accessed February 2024. Three rounds of TGS-GapCloser²⁷ v1.2.1, followed by one round of QuarTeT GapFiller were used on haplotype 1, haplotype 2. The first round used filtered high quality HiFi reads (Q20, length >10 kb) to fill medium sized gaps (<20,000 bases). The second round used filtered ONT reads (Q25, length >10 kb) to fill larger gaps (>20,000 bases), while the third round used polished unitigs (.p_utg.fa) of Hifiasm assembly. Gaps were reduced from N=4015 (haplotype 2) to N=2501 (haplotype 2) to N=1100 after TGS-GapCloser. Finally, all reference genomes and scaffold sets (p_utg) were used as combined input and gaps were reduced to N=550 (haplotype 2) after QuarTeT GapFiller ('default parameters -q *.fa')⁴⁰ v1.2.1.

[Main Assembly] Targeted Haplotype-Aware Genome Polishing with Pilon

To enhance the accuracy and quality values (QV) of the haplotype assemblies of *C. macrocephalus* and to precisely polish the genome assembly while correcting error-prone regions, we performed k-mer analysis, read alignments, and sequence polishing using Pilon⁴¹ v1.24.

- 1. Identification of missing reads at assembly seq-mers error positions:** Positions of erroneous k-mers of non-repetitive k-mers found in the genome (i.e., the error seqmers) were identified with Merqury⁴² and Meryl⁴², as explained in the T2T-Polish GitHub workflow ("QV estimate with hybrid k-mer db"; <https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>). K-mers were counted using Meryl ('meryl count k=\$k') for each haplotype assembly, and a combined (hybrid) 21-mers from Illumina and HiFi data Meryl k-mer database was created through union-summing ('meryl union-sum'). We further filtered the k-mers from the hybrid read database, retaining only those k-mers with higher multiplicity values, such as greater than 5 or 10 ('meryl greater-than'), to eliminate low-confidence sequences. Next, the k-mers unique to the reads and absent from the assemblies were isolated using Meryl's difference operation ('meryl difference'). These read-only k-mers represented genomic variation not captured in the assemblies. We used these filtered k-mers to extract reads containing these unique sequences from both the Illumina and HiFi datasets using the lookup command ('meryl-lookup').
- 2. Mapping of reads:** We started with high-quality sequencing reads. ONT reads were filtered using NanoFilt to remove low-quality bases, while for Illumina paired-end reads (R1 and R2), we removed low-quality sequences and adapter contamination using Fastp ('-5 -3 -n 0 -f 5 -F 5 -t 5 -T 5 -q 20')⁴³ v0.23.4. Next, HiFi reads were aligned the combined haplotype assemblies using Winnowmap based on k-mers found in repeats ('-W repetitive_k15.txt'). For ONT reads, we used Minimap2 ('map-ont') without secondary alignments ('-secondary=no') and alignments were filtered at MAPQ >30 ('-q 30'). Illumina short-reads were aligned using Bowtie2⁴⁴ end-to-end (sensitive mode) ('-sensitive') to minimize spurious alignments, with no mixed read pairs ('-no-mixed') and no discordant mappings ('-no-discordant') to keep only alignments no farther than the expected insert size (500 pb.+ 2 * read length, for Illumina data), finally PCR duplicates were removed using Samtools command ('markdup').
- 3. Running pilon and calling the consensus:** Pilon was then used to refine the assemblies by correcting SNPs, indels, and other base-level errors. For each haplotype scaffold, Pilon was run with specific parameters ('-genome, -frags, -bam, -targets, -fix all, -vcf, -diploid, -minmq 30, -minqual 30') to use the alignments from all data types (HiFi, ONT, and short reads). The output VCF files containing the detected variants were sorted by position using ('bcftools sort'), compressed using bgzip, and indexed using ('bcftools index'), and a consensus sequence was generated for each scaffold using ('bcftools consensus -f \$genome.fa -H 1').

The overall median Quality Value increased from 41 to approximately 45-47 after haplotype-aware targeted assembly polishing.

[Main assembly] Additional Hi-C Scaffolding and Sequence Integration Using Quartet

To reintegrate unplaced scaffolds in each haplotype in the pseudo-chromosomes, we used Quartet and HapHiC. First, we aligned the unplaced contigs to reference genome *C. fuscus* (GCA_030347435.1), and reference genome *C. gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2) using Quartet AssemblyMapper with the following parameters ('-r \$reference -q \$contigs -c 50000 -l 2000 -i 90 -a Minimap2'). We identified 53 MB and 33 MB of unplaced scaffold sequences in bighead catfish haplotype 1 and haplotype 2, respectively, with strong homology to *C. fuscus* pseudo-chromosomes; we filtered bighead catfish haplotype 1 and haplotype 2 with SeqKit to retain pseudo-chromosomes and concatenated them to unplaced scaffolds. For the preparation of Hi-C scaffolding, Hi-C reads were mapped to separate haplotypes using BWA-MEM ('-5SP') after making a BWT index for haplotype 1 and haplotype 2 ('bwa index \$genome.fasta'), and Hi-C read alignments filtered for PCR duplicates and secondary alignments ('samblaster \$BAM | samtools view - -@ \$threads -S -h -b -F 3340') with Samblaster⁴⁵ v0.1.26. Hi-C scaffolding was performed on bighead catfish haplotypes using HapHiC⁴⁶ v1.0. The resulting Hi-C maps were visualized in JBAT and using ('haphic plot') for separate scaffolds from each haplotype (**Figure 3** and **Figure 4**) but also with all scaffolds represented in a wide-map (**Figure 5**), and a post-review of the Hi-C scaffold was performed as described in the previous section. Finally, three rounds of TGS-GapCloser followed by one round of targeted Pilon polishing specifying the new targets resulted in a genome of global higher quality (i.e., both in term of QV quality values and CRAQ CRE/CSE structural accuracy). We addressed the duplication errors visible in the heterozygous peak of the k-mer coverage from the Merqury spectra by using haplotype-specific k-mer databases. This involved applying ('meryl difference') command to identify erroneous k-mers and using ('meryl-lookup') command to extract reads associated with these k-mers. Finally, we used BCFtools to call a consensus using the opposite haplotype ('-H 1') within bcftools consensus command, effectively reversing most haplotype switch errors.

[Main assembly] Additional Targeted Consensus Automated Polishing (SVs and SNPs)

Consensus polishing was automated by following instructions from the T2T-polish GitHub repository <https://github.com/arangrhie/T2T-Polish>. A HiFi mapping file of repetitive k-mers (k=15) was generated with Meryl and used in Winnowmap for HiFi read alignment ('-MD -W .repetitive_k15.txt -ax map-pb'), followed by alignment filtering with Samtools ('-Sb'). pb-falconc ('bam-filter-clipped -t -F 0x104 -output-count-fn') v1.15.0 was then used to filter clipped reads. Genome polishing was performed using the liftover branch of the Racon GitHub repository, using Racon with ('-L -S') options⁴⁷ v1.5.0. After polishing, the k-mers present in the genome (seqmers) were counted using Meryl count (k=21). Merfin was then applied ('-readmers Illumina.HiFi.gtl.PCRfree.hybrid.meryl-seqmers') to evaluate the results by comparing the distributions in the reads and in the polished genome^{31,48}. For consensus generation (i.e., to apply polishing edits to the genome assembly), we used BCFtools ('-H 1') for two rounds of genome correction. Assembly quality metrics were measured for QV, completeness and BUSCOs scores, we found a large increase in QV in most chromosomes (min. increase >+1-5 QV points) after ONT Racon and Merfin, the median QV was 50, the progress over months is presented in **Figure 6**.

[Main assembly] Organelles: Bighead Catfish Mitochondrial Genome

The mitochondrial genome was assembled by mapping to reference (NC_046749.1) bighead catfish mtDNA, available at NCBI Nucleotide. Minimap2 ('-ax map-ont -secondary=no') mapped nanopore reads to the reference and Minimap2 ('-ax sr') mapped Illumina reads. PCR duplicates in short reads were removed from the alignments using Samtools and the results were visualized in IGV. Pilon ('-fix all -diploid -changes -vcf -tracks -minmq 10') was used to correct (NC_046749.1) and call SNPs, SVs, gaps and local variants and obtain the consensus mtDNA sequence. Reads were re-aligned to the consensus and no more SNPs were visible in the IGV. Next, mapped reads were filtered with samtools view ('-F4 -q 20') and re-assembled de novo with Unicycler⁴⁹ for comparison. The results were visualized in Bandage-ng² v2022.09. The assembly was polished with Pilon and the two homologous mitochondria were compared using Minimap2 ('-eqx -x asm5'). Gene annotations were generated using MitoFinder⁵⁰ v1.4.2. To ensure that the mitochondrial genome was correct and not dissimilar to other mtDNAs in Siluriformes, we downloaded all reference mtDNA sequences for (N=209) species of Siluriformes catfish from NCBI Nucleotide, last accessed September 2024. All sequences were taken from in NCBI RefSeq and not from NCBI GenBank. All mtDNA nucleotide sequences (N=210) were renamed to the Pan-SN naming scheme (<https://github.com/pangenome/PanSN-spec>), concatenated in a single multi-FASTA including the bighead catfish mtDNA generated here after Pilon, and all-versus-all alignments were performed with wfmash, then ODGI was used to filter the alignment graph, and visualizations were made with Bandage and multiQC⁵¹. All tools of the pipeline were part of the larger PGGB (Pan Genome Graph Builder)⁵². The results of the alignments are shown in **Supplementary Figure 2**, the mtDNA aligns well with other sequences in the phylogenetic order and is not an outlier. Therefore, we conclude that the mtDNA sequence is valid and hereby appended it sequence to the multi-FASTA of bighead catfish haplotype 1.

[Main assembly] Transposable Element Annotation Pipeline

Two methods were used to discover transposable elements (TEs) in the bighead catfish genome: 1. a species-specific TE library was generated de novo for the bighead catfish, 2. TE libraries of fish species were retrieved from the internet (FishTEDB database) and used as a fish TE library.

De novo transposable element library for bighead catfish

De novo TE annotation was performed using EDTA (Extensive de novo TE Annotator)⁵³ v2.2.0. The pipeline integrates several tools to detect different element types. LTRharvest⁵⁴ v1.5.10 identifies LTR retrotransposons by efficiently locating structural features such as border positions, LTR lengths, and motifs in large genomic datasets. LTR FINDER⁵⁵ and the parallel version of LTR_FINDER⁵⁶ v1.1.0 accelerate LTR detection using parallel computing for large genomes. LTR_retriever⁵⁷ v2.9.0 refines LTR annotations to improve accuracy and remove false positives. TESorter: an accurate and fast way to classify LTR retrotransposons⁵⁸ v1.4.7, GRF (Generic Repeat Finder)⁵⁹ v1.1 for genome-wide de novo repeat detection. TIR-Learner⁶⁰ v1.1.2 uses machine learning to detect terminal inverted repeat (TIR) transposons, including miniature inverted TEs (MITEs). HelitronScanner⁶¹ v1.0 identifies Helitrons by recognizing their characteristic structural motifs. RepeatModeler⁶² v2.0.3 performs de novo repeat discovery and builds a comprehensive repeat library. MAFFT⁶³ v7.526 is used for multiple sequence alignments, and HMMER⁶⁴ v3.4 is used for domain-based searching and TE classification. TEs in bighead catfish were found to occupy approximately 35.25% of the genome, with 19.12% for TIR DNA transposons, 4.47% for Helitrons, and 8.30% for LTR retrotransposons, and uncharacterized repeats accounting for 2.82% (**Table 1**).

FishTEDB general fish-specific TE library collection

Next, libraries of TE consensus sequences for transposons were retrieved from the FishTEDB database, version 1⁶⁵, which contains different species of fish and their associated transposable element libraries in FASTA file format, and these sequences were merged with EDTA's denovo bighead catfish initial TE annotations. To reduce the library complexity and to create a non-redundant TE library (i.e., to lower the number of sequences and redundancy of the combined TE library dataset), we used CD-HIT-EST ('-d 20 -aS 0.95 -c 0.95 -G 0 -g 1 -b 500')⁶⁶ for an 80% identity threshold and 80% alignment coverage of TE sequences in all-against-all sequence clustering following the commonly used 80%-80% rule⁶⁷. The reduced TE library was used to mask (i.e., to annotate) the bighead catfish genome for TEs with RepeatMasker (Smit, AFA, Hubley, R. & Green, P RepeatMasker at <http://www.repeatmasker.org>).

[Main assembly] Benchmarking of Assembly Quality Metrics

Metrics of continuity, structural accuracy, base accuracy, and functional completeness were used for benchmarking as described in the Vertebrate Genome Project (VGP) paper⁷. Assembly Quality Metrics are presented in **Table 2** and the methodology for their calculation is presented below:

1. **Continuity and summary statistics:** To evaluate the continuity and summary statistics of the assembly, we compute the following measures for scaffold/contig (N50, N90, NG50, LG50, and LG90) using RagTag ('ragtag.py asmstats -g')² v2.1.0.
2. **Repeat completeness and continuity of repeats:** To measure repeat completeness and repeat continuity to assess assembly quality, we estimated the percentage of fully assembled LTR retroelements (LTR-RTs) and calculated the long terminal repeat (LTR) assembly index (LAI) using two reference-free programs, LTR Assembly Index (LAI)⁶⁸ and LTR_retriever⁵⁷ v2.9.00. Telomeres are nucleoprotein complexes located at the ends of eukaryotic chromosomes⁶⁹, they are found in all vertebrates studied so far, the DNA component of telomeres contains a tandemly repeated G-rich hexanucleotide sequence (TTAGGG/CCCTAA)ⁿ.^{70,71} To assess the assembly quality of complex repeats (centromeres), we used TandemTools and TandemQUAST³⁰ v1.0 (results not shown). Telomere prediction for presence/absence and orientation of telomeres was done with TIDK, a Telomere Identification Toolkit, implemented in TeloExplorer ('-m 50 -c animal'), a module of QuarTeT. To estimate gap length and their location in genome, we used detgaps, a script from Asset, available on GitHub (<https://github.com/dfguan/asset>).
3. **Structural accuracy (regional and structural errors and reliable blocks):** To assess structural accuracy, we used CRAQ ('sms_coverage=6, ngs_coverage=20, -Minimap2-sensitive')²⁶ v1.0.9, CRAQ is a method that relies on examining mapped reads, clipped reads, and coverage support from two or more simultaneous sequencing platforms against a reference, to find supporting regions (i.e., the reliable blocks in the VGP paper⁷). CRAQ metrics consisted of global AQI (R-AQI & S-AQI): Small Clip-based Regional Errors (CREs) and Large Clip-based Structural Errors (CSEs), which indicate incorrect assembly breakpoints. Mapping results consisted in loading multiple read-to-genome alignment files in the BAM file format, along with BED, and BigWig genome annotation files, all were visualized using the Integrative Genome Viewer (IGV)⁷² using the command line ('igv -g \$genome.fa \$BAM ..

). To assess cross-species structural correctness, we used the same references from related catfish species for one-to-one nucleotide-level alignments of orthologous segments using MashMap2 (`'-s 2000000 -pi 90 -c 100000'`)⁷³ v3.1.3.

4. **Base accuracy and assembly completeness:** To assess base accuracy and completeness, specifically Mercury's quality values (QV) and 21-mer genome completeness (%), we used Mercury⁴² v1.3. Mercury was run three times using different k-mer databases: Illumina, HiFi, and a hybrid 21-mer database combining Illumina and HiFi reads, using the method described in the "Consensus polishing" section above. To assess functional completeness and evaluate gene set completeness, we used the ray-finned fish lineage and BUSCO (`'-l actinopterygii_odb10'`)⁷⁴ v5.6.1. Finally, mapping rates and inconsistencies were determined by mapping using Minimap2 (`'-ax map-hifi -secondary=no'`) and Winnowmap (`'-W repetitive.15.txt'`) at MAPQ >10 for HiFi reads, while for ONT reads we used the map-ont default for Minimap2 and the map-pb default in Winnowmap MAPQ >10 read-to-assembly alignments. Visualizations used IGV (`'igv -g $genome $BAM(s) $mercury_only_bed_wig_kmer_files'`).

NCBI Submissions

The final scaffolds were validated using the NCBI Foreign Contamination Screen (FCS) tool and submitted to NCBI following the Vertebrate Genome Project naming conventions⁷.

Data Records

Data sets are hosted under the NCBI BioProject number ([PRJNA1132508](#)) and the diploid Bighead Catfish BioSample accession number is ([SAMN41769988](#)). Raw sequenced reads are hosted at NCBI SRA ([SRR29723576](#), [SRR29723575](#), [SRR29723577](#), [SRR29723578](#)) for Nanopore, HiFi, Hi-C, and Illumina, respectively. The assembled genome has been deposited at GenBank under the accession numbers [XXX](#) for haplotype 1 and [XXX](#) for haplotype 2.

Technical Validation

Technical validation of haplotype-resolved assemblies

The haplotype-resolved de novo genome assembly resulted in 27 Hi-C scaffolds, corresponding to the expected chromosome number of $2n = 2x = 54$ pseudo-chromosomes. The chromosomal arrangement was consistent with metaphase karyotyping, further confirming the accuracy of the assembly. Mercury analysis identified missing data in raw sequencing reads (read-only grey peak) meaning that some of the genome data was not recovered in the final assembly, this may in fact be the consequence of genome complexity and suboptimal assembly parameters (**Figure 7A**), which indicates that the few percents of missing buscos (**Figure 7B**) visible in the Flye version of the bighead genome assembly, these may eventually be recovered in the future. Finally for Mercury, we identified a small multiplicity peak at 3x (green color), which indicates small amount of sequence false duplication which would have been eventually corrected by purging the assembly which tools such as PurgeDups⁷⁵ or Purge Haplotigs⁷⁶ prior to Hi-C scaffolding, specifically after the hifiasm step (**Figure 7C**). Sequence variation analysis was performed with PlotSR suite⁷⁷, revealed 1,968,666 heterozygous SNPs across both haplotypes after Minimap2 "asm5" cross-haplotype mapping, resulting in a heterozygosity rate of 0.594%. Structural variant analysis identified 392,973 insertions, totaling 7.67 Mb in haplotype 2, while haplotype 1 contained 393,127 deletions, spanning 7.75 Mb. Copy number variations included 114 copy gains in haplotype 2, covering 184 Kb, and 123 copy losses in haplotype 1, totaling 416 Kb. Highly divergent genomic regions were identified, spanning approximately 57.9 Mb in haplotype 1 and 56.0 Mb in haplotype 2. Additionally, 47 tandem repeat clusters were detected, covering 10 Kb in haplotype 1 and 7 Kb in haplotype 2. Transposable element (TE) annotation indicated that 35.25% of the genome consisted of repetitive sequences. Among these, TIR DNA transposons accounted for 19.12%, Helitrons comprised 4.47%, LTR retrotransposons made up 8.30%, LINE elements represented 0.46%, and the remaining 2.82% consisted of uncharacterized repeats.

Macroscopy analysis

To examine orthologous relationships and identify syntenic regions between catfish and related teleost species, we obtained proteomes (.pep.fa files) from Ensembl, ensuring the latest assembly versions to maintain consistency in analyses. Selected species included *Oncorhynchus mykiss* (USDA_OmykA_1.1), *Oryzias latipes* (ASM223467v1), *Cyprinus carpio* (Cypcar_WagV4.0), *Oreochromis niloticus* (O_niloticus_UMD_NMBU), *Danio rerio* (GRCz11), *Lates calcarifer* (ASB_HGAPassembly_v1), and *Lepisosteus oculatus* (LepOcu1). Orthologous gene clusters (Orthogroups) were first identified with OrthoFinder (`'orthofinder -f /proteomes -M msa -a 126 -t 126'`) v2.5.5. Subsequently, we utilized xrbxpress and macrosyntR to analyze the resulting orthogroups and visualize their syntenic relationships across species. This combined approach allowed for an in-depth view of conserved and divergent genomic regions, providing insights into evolutionary adaptations and functional diversity within the catfish lineage and related teleosts (**Figure 8**).

Discussion

High-quality and complete reference genome assemblies of animal species are essential for genomic applications in agriculture, species conservation, and understanding genetic diversity. The bighead catfish genome assembly ("fClMacL1.0") using the Hifiasm+GreenHill pipeline resulted in two homologous haplotype-resolved sequences (haplotype 1 and haplotype 2). Additionally, we produced a collapsed diploid assembly with Flye, representing a single mosaic haplotype (though not submitted to NCBI). No major limitations were encountered at this stage.

The Hi-C scaffolding process, while labor-intensive, successfully yielded 27 pseudo-chromosomes per haplotype, consistent with previously reported karyotype studies. Cross-validation confirmed that the chromosomal organization aligned with cytogenetic observations. Mapping rates of 99% indicate high sequence accuracy and the absence of artificial sequence artifacts. However, the genome assembly's overall data retention—estimated through k-mer completeness and BUSCO scores—was 2–5% lower than our previous bighead catfish genome assembly, suggesting that sequence completeness was somewhat affected, while the cause for sequence loss remains unknown.

Technical validation followed Vertebrate Genomes Project (VGP) benchmarks, using a k-mer size of 21 for QV analysis, a commonly applied value for low-heterozygosity animal genomes. Raw sequencing reads contained minor contamination (detected via FCS NCBI tool and Mash), but no contaminants remained in the final submitted assemblies. Study limitations stem from low sequencing depth and poor ONT library quality, with the longest read limited to <134 kb due to DNA degradation during transportation. Software-related issues also contributed to challenges, particularly the lack of tool maintenance, absence of quality control, and software instability during assembly.

The species *C. macrocephalus* is not widely farmed on a commercial scale but is highly valued for its firm, yellow-fleshed meat and is often crossbred with *C. gariepinus* to enhance growth rates for aquaculture purposes. However, the expansion of hybrid and non-native *C. gariepinus* farming in the Mekong region has raised ecological concerns, particularly regarding genetic introgression and competition with native species. In Vietnam, successful captive breeding programs have domesticated *C. macrocephalus*, with hatchery populations maintained for approximately 30 generations in the Mekong Delta. Recent genomic studies on aquaculture species, including Atlantic salmon (*Salmo salar*) and Atlantic cod (*Gadus morhua*), have highlighted the potential of high-quality genome assemblies for understanding genetic traits and improving aquaculture productivity. However, previous efforts on *C. macrocephalus* have been constrained by technological and resource limitations, resulting in fragmented assemblies or low-quality draft genomes. Additionally, a reference genome for *C. macrocephalus* would allow targeted genetically modified broodstock, similar to what has been achieved in Nile tilapia (*Oreochromis niloticus*). By filling critical gaps in our understanding of *C. macrocephalus*, this study lays the groundwork for leveraging genomic insights in selective breeding programs and conservation. Specifically, the new high-quality, chromosome-scale, haplotype-resolved genome assembly of the bighead catfish provides a robust framework for investigating genetic diversity, structural variants, and adaptive traits, while also enabling comparative genomic analyses with closely related species such as *C. gariepinus* and *C. fuscus*.

Conclusions

The final assembly achieved a total size of twice 880 Mb, representing the two haploid genomes of *C. macrocephalus* across 27 chromosomes. The assembly quality was confirmed by a QV of around 50, 96% k-mer completeness, and 94% BUSCO completeness. Structural integrity was supported by Hi-C maps qualitative visual assessment and comparative analysis with related *Clarias* genomes. The assembly in its current state contains at most 300 unresolved regions/gaps, significantly fewer than earlier efforts, providing a comprehensive view of the *C. macrocephalus* genome. This assembly will enable functional genomic studies, facilitate research into the species' evolutionary history, and support conservation strategies and aquaculture improvements.

In conclusion, this is the first chromosome-level haplotype-resolved assembly sequence for bighead catfish *C. macrocephalus*, providing an excellent genetic resource for downstream comparative genomics and related applications, such as the study of structural variation for genes of agricultural interest for trait improvement (e.g., *MSTN*, *IGF1*, and *GH* for growth; *IgM*, *IgD*, *TLR*, and *MHC I* for immunity; and *HSP70*, *AHR*, and *CYP1A* for environmental resistance and pond fitness) or for designing CRISPR guide RNAs for gene editing, ultimately benefiting Thailand and Vietnam.

Usage Notes

The primary assembly can be used for comparative genomics studies involving synteny because the completeness of the gene set is higher, while for studies involving variant analysis, either haplotype 1 or haplotype 2 can be used.

Code availability

No custom software codes were developed as part of this research. All bioinformatics tools and pipelines were executed following the manual and protocols provided by the respective software developers. The versions of the software used, along with their corresponding parameters, have been thoroughly described in the Methods section.

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Acknowledgements

We thank the NSTDA Supercomputer Center (<https://thaisc.io/>) for providing cutting-edge High-Performance Computing (HPC) research and service computational resources through the LANTA supercomputer and exceptional customer support. Additionally, we are extremely grateful to Zeng Xiaofei, for helping to set up HapHiC software parameters through extensive GitHub discussions. Special thanks to the developer of GreenHill (ShunOuchi) for his invaluable comments and assistance in running GreenHill, the developer of Juicebox JBAT (Olga) for her feedback and support in troubleshooting 3D-DNA pipeline and in interpreting Hi-C maps, and the 3D-DNA community for their helpful discussions on how to run

Juicer in CPU mode. We extend our gratitude to the developers of QuarTeT for their active updates of the tool and contributions to the field.

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Author contributions statement

Genome assembly, analysis and data submissions were performed by Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres who also fully drafted the manuscript. Genomic DNA hybrid catfish sample preparation and sequencing outsourcing was managed by Dr. Worapong Singchat. Project conceptualization, supervision, and its funding was led by Dr. Kornorn Srikulnath.

Competing interests

The corresponding author, Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres, certifies on behalf of all authors that there are no competing interests in this project. Quentin Ludovic Stephane Andres joined the AGB research unit after the DNA sample preparation step. The research is solely aimed at improving aquaculture practices and outcomes.

Supplementary Methods

Quality-Control and Preparation Experiment of Sequenced Reads

Raw sequencing reads were evaluated for quality using FastQC (<http://www.bioinformatics.babraham.ac.uk/projects/fastqc/>) v0.1.12 for short reads and NanoPlot⁷⁸ v1.42.0 for long reads. Sequencing depth and fastq QC (base/quality summary) was calculated with SeqKit³⁷, and Seqtk (<https://github.com/lh3/seqtk>). Illumina data, but not Hi-C data, have been trimmed for synthetic sequencing adapters using AdapterRemoval⁷⁹ v2.3.3. PacBio's HiFi reads were trimmed using HiFiAdapterFilt ('-reward 1 -penalty -5 -gapopen 3 -gapextend 3 -dust no -soft_masking true -evaluate 700 -searchsp 1750000000000')⁸⁰ v64d1c7b. Cross-species contamination raw read data was evaluated against the Mash databases ('refseq.genomes + plasmids.k21.s1000.msh') using Mash ('sketch size=1000, k=21')⁸¹ v2.3. Reads were filtered for quality of length whenever necessary using NanoFilt ('-l \$length -q \$Quality')⁸² v2.8.0.

PacBio HiFi long reads

PacBio HiFi reads (*library source: genomic, library selection: circular consensus sequencing (CSS)/PCR*) were generated using circular consensus sequencing (CSS). This method achieves a base accuracy of >99.9%, maximizing assembly quality by sequencing multiple times the same DNA fragment in a continuous polymerase chain reaction (PCR) without denaturation¹⁴. Sequencing on the Sequel II system produced 10.62 Gb of raw data, representing 12.9X genome coverage. The dataset achieved a mean quality score of Q28.7 and a median of Q36, with over 72% of reads scoring above Q30 (**Figure 1C**).

Oxford Nanopore Technologies (ONT) non-UL 1D-long noisy reads

Oxford Nanopore (ONT) reads (*library source: genomic, library selection: size fractionation*) provided long, noisy data with a median error rate of around 20%. ONT reads can improve assembly continuity and span complex repeat regions¹⁵. These were prepared from size-selected, end-polished DNA fragments with adapters ligated to double-stranded DNA and purified with AMPure XP beads. Sequencing on a PromethION system generated 29.56 Gb of raw data, equivalent to 36X genome coverage, with 13 kb N50 read length. The median quality score was Q11.03 and 97.0% of the reads were above Q7 (**Figure 1D**).

Proximity-ligation (Hi-C) Illumina paired-end short reads

Hi-C data (*library source: genomic, library selection: DNase*) were generated using proximity-ligation techniques to provide long-range linkage information, allowing contig phasing (haplotype separation) and genome scaffolding^{16,17}. Generated using an in situ Hi-C protocol² with DpnII endonuclease digestion² and sequenced on the Illumina NextSeq2000, the data contained 37.19 Gb of paired-end reads, achieving 39.77X genome coverage. The quality of the data was high, yielding 123.96M read pairs and 74.77M unique Hi-C contacts, with >97.18% at Q30.

Illumina paired-end short reads

Illumina paired-end short reads¹⁸ (*library source: genomic, library selection: PCR*) were sequenced on an Illumina NextSeq2000 platform which yielded 31.91 Gb of raw read data (read length = 151 bp) with 40X genome coverage. The average quality score was Q25, and 92% of the reads were above Q30.

Reference-Free Genome Profiling Survey

All reference-free genome profiling analyses were performed using the K-mer Analysis Toolkit (KAT)²⁰ v2.4.1 and GenomeScope¹⁹ v2.0. For the genome survey, canonical 21-mer k-mer distributions were estimated from trimmed Illumina and HiFi reads using Meryl⁴² and Jellyfish⁸³ v2.3.1. Genome survey predicted a haploid sequence length of approximately 890 million nucleotides (Mb.) and an inter-haplotype heterozygosity rate of approximately 0.549% for bighead catfish (**Figure 1B**). For base accuracy and phasing error correction, polishing tools used various methods, for pileup-based methods we used Pilon, which corrected pileup based and SNP switch errors previously identified with Meryl based on Merqury position of assembly errors (hereby referred to as "error seqmers")⁴², Inspector⁸⁴ was used to assess assembly quality and sometimes repair structural errors, pileup errors and base-errors with its correct module based on HiFi reads. While Racon with Merfin HiFi or Clair3 with Merfin HiFi effectively handled SNPs and other types of small nucleotide variants (SNVs) especially under low coverage. Nanopore-based polishing was always followed by HiFi polishing to maintain high base accuracy. TGS-GapCloser was used to bridge gaps, CRAQ was applied to break assemblies at read hard-clipping points, and JBAT/HiC scaffolding, followed by manual review, ensured structural accuracy. Each step logically depended on prior outputs: For instance, JBAT scaffolding necessitated subsequent gap closing (e.g., TGS-GapCloser), while iterative refinement employed tools such as Racon or bcftools consensus command from BCFtools. The final genome assembly was required to have high mapping quality, with no MAPQ0 regions, and an overall QV > 50. Variant calls were validated visually using IGV and overall quality and structural consistency were assessed with Meryl and Asset/detgaps, CRAQ, Inspector and VerityMap.

Figures & Tables

Figure 1. Sequencing Data Summary for (*Clarias macrocephalus*) Genome Experiment. (A) Sequencing and data types. (B) GenomeScope profile for bighead catfish at $k=21$, estimating genome size at 899 Mb. (haploid) with 0.056% heterozygosity between haplotypes. (C) Quality and length of HiFi reads. (D) Quality and length of ONT reads.

Figure 2. Comprehensive Haplotype-Resolved Genome Assembly and Scaffolding Workflow for Bighead Catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*). (A) A photograph of the bighead catfish (*Clarias macrocephalus*), the subject of the genome assembly study. (B) Karyotype analysis of *C. macrocephalus* (maneechot at al., 2016), indicating 27 chromosome pairs. (C) Scaffolding results using Juicebox v2.16.0. (D) Genome assembly strategy using PacBio HiFi, ONT, and Illumina reads, followed by consensus and haplotype-resolved assembly using Hifiasm (Hi-C UL mode). (E) Genome scaffolding using Hi-C reads, processed through GreenHill, 3D-DNA, and Juicer tools, producing haplotype-resolved and consensus assemblies. (F) Mitochondrial genome assembly (mtDNA) leveraging Minimap2 and MitoHiFi pipelines. (G) Final assembly improvements include multiple gap-filling rounds with TGS-GapCloser, QuarTeT GapFiller, and polishing with NextPolish2, producing high-quality pseudo-chromosomes and unplaced scaffolds. Various software pipelines and sequencing data types are used throughout the assembly process, as indicated by the icons.

Features	Haplotype 1	Haplotype 2
Overall quality (x.y.P.Q.C)	x.y.P.Q.C 6.30.P7.53.Q48.C94.25	x.y.P.Q.C 6.30.P7.53.Q48.C94.25
Genome size (Mb)	875 Mb	880 Mb
Number of pseudo-chromosomes	27	27
Mitochondria genome assembly (bp)	16,510 bp	N/A
NG50 of contigs (Mb)	3 Mb	3 Mb
N50 of scaffolds (Mb)	34 Mb	34 Mb
LG50/LG90 of scaffolds	11 / 24 (Hap1)	11 / 24 (Hap2)
Number of gaps	752	653
GC content (%)	39.32%	39.32%
Complete BUSCOs N (%)	93.0% (Hap1)	93.5% (Hap2)
Median QV (Merqury k21)	42.99 (Hap1)	43.33 (Hap2) 48.2251 (Combined)
Genome completeness (Merqury k21)	89.1141 (Hap1)	88.8801 (Hap2) 95.2538 (Combined)
Transposable Elements Superfamily	# of elements	
LINE	–	
I	128	
L1	547	
L2	1,129	
Rex	556	
LINE/Unknown	7,412	
LTR	–	
Bel_Pao	151	
Copia	53	
Gypsy	68,215	
LTR/Unknown	134,66	
TIR	–	
CACTA	357,388	
Mutator	172,578	
PIF_Harbinger	36,538	
Tc1_Mariner	41,5	
hAT	80,189	
PiggyBac	758	
Polinton	281	
NonLTR	–	
DIRS_YR	678	
Penelope	417	
NonTIR	–	
Helitron	166,251	
Repeat Fragment	78,9	
Total Interspersed	1,148,329	
Feature	Statistics	
Raw bases and depth of PacBio HiFi (Gb)	10.62 Gb eq. 13X (diploid)	
Raw bases and depth of WGS-Illumina (Gb)	31.91 Gb eq. 40X (diploid)	
Raw bases and depth of Hi-C reads (Gb)	37.19 Gb eq. 40X (diploid)	
Raw bases and depth of ONT reads (Gb)	29.56 Gb eq. 36X (diploid)	
Genome survey	(GenomeScope2.0, k=21)	
Homozygous (aa)	99.4731% (min), 99.4852% (max)	
Heterozygous (ab)	0.514823% (min), 0.526938% (max)	
Genome Haploid Length	888,507,041 bp (min), 889,248,923 bp (max)	
Genome Repeat Length	216,723,513 bp (min), 216,904,472 bp (max)	
Genome Unique Length	671,783,528 bp (min), 672,344,451 bp (max)	
Model Fit	77.1496% (min), 96.9705% (max)	
Read Error Rate	0.06%	

Table 1. Summary Statistics of the Haplotype-Resolved *Clarias macrocephalus* Genome Assembly and Transposable Element Content. Note that assembly metrics and transposable element content were measured on pseudo-chromosomes only (excluding Unplaced scaffolds), transposable element content was only measured for the haplotype 2

Scaffold Name	Size	Errors	Quality Values	Gaps	Left Telomere	Right Telomere	S-AQI
Haplotype_Linkage	(Mb)	21-mer	hyb.k21.meryl	(N)	(5') AACCCCT)	(AGGGTT 3')	(%)
fClaMac_1_LG_01	48,4	3242	54.8396	23	Left 507 (-)	-	93.24
fClaMac_1_LG_02	46,18	6400	51.574	24	Left 607 (+)	Right 1016 (-)	73.94
fClaMac_1_LG_03	40,54	6784	50.6951	20	-	Right 215 (-)	91.18
fClaMac_1_LG_04	37,64	4160	52.7678	23	Left 147 (+)	Right 122 (-)	100.00
fClaMac_1_LG_05	37,19	9007	49.2436	23	Left 579 (+)	Right 190 (-)	93.23
fClaMac_1_LG_06	37,01	5548	51.4013	25	-	-	84.09
fClaMac_1_LG_07	34,64	7089	49.8928	25	Left 214 (+)	-	93.24
fClaMac_1_LG_08	47,03	12668	48.7208	32	Left 170 (+)	Right 190 (-)	89.37
fClaMac_1_LG_09	28,28	7205	49.2196	13	Left 153 (+)	Right 1630 (-)	81.31
fClaMac_1_LG_10	29,87	12042	47.0424	24	Left 282 (+)	-	95.23
fClaMac_1_LG_11	25,51	6087	49.3463	19	Left 1008 (+)	-	80.92
fClaMac_1_LG_12	28,04	8367	48.2834	21	Left 124 (+)	-	95.73
fClaMac_1_LG_13	24,08	3715	51.2825	18	Left 377 (+)	-	86.62
fClaMac_1_LG_14	21,22	4707	49.7286	13	-	Right 136 (-)	94.05
fClaMac_1_LG_15	25,46	3974	51.1515	20	Left 127 (+)	Right 115 (-)	95.00
fClaMac_1_LG_16	24,8	4054	50.9451	15	-	Right 109 (-)	73.65
fClaMac_1_LG_17	22,98	67523	38.5013	15	Left 120 (+)	-	77.54
fClaMac_1_LG_18	24,8	2060	53.9205	13	-	-	90.26
fClaMac_1_LG_19	31,01	3329	52.8263	22	-	Right 363 (-)	92.45
fClaMac_1_LG_20	30,49	4074	51.8251	15	-	Right 406 (-)	83.79
fClaMac_1_LG_21	28,95	4609	51.2	28	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_1_LG_22	33,48	2784	54.0062	23	-	Right 904 (-)	92.37
fClaMac_1_LG_23	31,45	8435	48.8646	16	-	Right 790 (-)	86.84
fClaMac_1_LG_24	28,07	4984	50.6636	12	Left 423 (+)	-	88.33
fClaMac_1_LG_25	38,33	6711	50.6434	24	-	-	96.55
fClaMac_1_LG_26	40,06	4967	52.1555	21	Left 556 (+)	Right 604 (-)	87.85
fClaMac_1_LG_27	29,17	2146	54.5417	13	-	-	74.96
fClaMac_2_LG_01	51,51	2649	55.5298	17	-	-	89.28
fClaMac_2_LG_02	44,94	6893	51.161	25	Left 255 (+)	-	71.62
fClaMac_2_LG_03	39,44	8894	49.5912	16	-	-	83.57
fClaMac_2_LG_04	38,01	6912	50.5588	18	Left 293 (+)	Right 526 (-)	88.17
fClaMac_2_LG_05	38,16	3424	53.4601	23	-	Right 125 (-)	78.26
fClaMac_2_LG_06	38,66	2675	54.3325	17	-	-	80.86
fClaMac_2_LG_07	33,93	5651	50.8217	17	Left 169 (+)	-	89.91
fClaMac_2_LG_08	47,19	10458	49.5856	29	Left 174 (+)	Right 190 (-)	89.44
fClaMac_2_LG_09	28,8	10239	47.5736	14	Left 641 (+)	-	91.91
fClaMac_2_LG_10	29,07	5001	50.8593	14	Left 268 (+)	-	95.24
fClaMac_2_LG_11	25,76	6627	48.9338	21	-	-	89.75
fClaMac_2_LG_12	30,93	6915	48.7951	19	-	-	82.58
fClaMac_2_LG_13	23,66	3213	51.9117	15	-	Right 100 (+)	86.65
fClaMac_2_LG_14	21,06	3487	50.9324	7	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_15	24,93	7673	48.2988	17	Left 134 (+)	Right 137 (-)	85.58
fClaMac_2_LG_16	24,83	3011	52.2777	10	-	-	81.74
fClaMac_2_LG_17	22,34	2012	53.6414	15	Left 175 (+)	-	85.99
fClaMac_2_LG_18	24,44	1986	54.0521	11	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_19	30,86	3566	52.521	16	-	Right 362 (-)	90.62
fClaMac_2_LG_20	34,51	2384	53.5357	13	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_21	27,99	2550	53.5741	13	-	-	100.00
fClaMac_2_LG_22	33,35	4588	51.8225	16	Left 128 (+)	Right 908 (-)	88.64
fClaMac_2_LG_23	31,45	9701	48.2459	6	Left 214 (+)	Right 793 (-)	82.68
fClaMac_2_LG_24	27,39	2840	53.0349	6	Left 114 (+)	-	93.87
fClaMac_2_LG_25	37,88	7891	49.9914	15	-	-	87.01
fClaMac_2_LG_26	40,17	11271	48.6822	13	-	Right 607 (-)	88.08
fClaMac_2_LG_27	29,56	1236	56.9751	12	Left 155 (+)	-	90.78
MT_from_NC_046749	0,02	-	-	-	-	-	-

Table 2. Summary of scaffold metrics in the haplotype-resolved genome assembly of *Clarias macrocephalus*. Metrics include Quality Values (QV) from Merqurey (k21 hybrid database), structural accuracy (S-AQI, %) from CRAQ, telomere orientation (+ for inward and - for outward repeats with >100 occurrences) from QuarTeT, and gap statistics identified using Detgaps (Asset).

Figure 3. Hi-C contact matrix heat maps displaying individual pseudo-chromosome scaffolds in haplotype 1, sorted by length.

Figure 4. Hi-C contact matrix heat maps displaying individual pseudo-chromosome scaffolds in haplotype 2.

Figure 5. Hi-C map of Hi-C scaffolds - Bighead Catfish. (A) Haplotype 1, blue. (B) Haplotype 2, purple

Figure 6. Assembly status January 2024 - November 2025. (A) Haplotype 1 (blue) and Haplotype 2 (purple) ideograms showing gaps on pseudo-chromosomes (orange rectangles) and telomeres (blue triangles) after manual-review in Juicebox (JBAT). (B) Same assemblies a few months later.

Figure 7. Visual representation of genome quality. (A) Merqury k-mer analysis spectra ASM of distinct copy k-mer in haplotype 1 and haplotype 2 of bighead catfish. (B) Merqury k-mer analysis spectra CN of copy number multiplicity of k-mers in the diploid bighead catfish assembly. There is limited evidence of false duplication (small homozygous peak at $k=3x$), which could be improved by purging homotype duplications or by trimming contig ends. (C) BUSCO assessment results in Flye haploid collapsed assembly showing high duplication rates and in Hifiasm haplotype-resolved assemblies showing minimal duplication rates.

Figure 8. Synteny analysis for various catfish samples. (A) Whole-genome 4-way synteny analysis from 1413 shared single-copy orthogroups across *Clarias gariepinus* (GCA_024256425.2), *Clarias macrocephalus*, *Danio rerio* (GRCz11) *Danio rerio* and *Oreochromis niloticus* (O_niloticus_UMD_NMBU), reveals conserved chromosome structures and rearrangements. (B) Simple phylogeny and geological timescales (TimeTree3).

Figure 9. SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE Post-Hifiasm HiC UL assembly genome Bandage graphs - Haplotype 1 and Haplotype 2. (A) Bandage graph after Hifiasm Hi-C UL assembly of Haplotype 1 (.hic.hap1.p_ctg.gfa). (B) Bandage graph after Hifiasm Hi-C UL assembly of Haplotype 2 (.hic.hap2.p_ctg.gfa)

Figure 10. SUPPLEMENTARY FIGURE All-versus-all 2D representations of mitochondrial DNA sequences alignments in Siluriformes catfishes. The mtDNA assembled for Bighead Catfish is on the last row (blue color) of the linear 2D representation.